

TOWARDS EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF CHRISTIAN RELIGIOUS EDUCATION FOR UNITY IN NIGERIA

POPOOLA Emmanuel Adebayo

Department of Christian Religious Studies, School of Arts and Social Sciences,
Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State
E-mail: popoolaea@fceiwo.edu.ng; +234 703 266 3525

Abstract

The series of violence, disputes and unrest being reported on daily basis shows there is much of discord in Nigeria. These ugly trends call for scholarly attention from the perspective of Christian Religious Education. This paper thematically focuses on the challenges and prospects of this important subject, Christian Religious Education. It further discusses Biblical instances of unity and how they can be adopted for national development. This paper argues that disunity retards the progress of any nation, Nigeria more specifically, and posits that government, at all levels, needs to accord Christian Religious Education much recognition in the school curriculum as a viable tool for addressing disunity in Nigeria; it also recommends that Nigerian citizens should to regularly evaluate themselves on scales of Biblical principles for unity and peaceful co-existence. The credible hope of the future is dependent on the tangible peace of the present, the continuous existence of Nigeria in the future is dependent on the peaceful existence of now.

Keywords: Discord, National Development, Disunity, Accord, Curriculum.

Introduction

The issue of disunity in Nigeria is worrisome and has elicited concerns from all and sundry; it has not evaded the attention of scholars, educators, religious leaders, politicians, business moguls and students, locally and internationally. Pages of newspapers and other media outlets, within and outside the country, are agog with reports of agitations from various ethno-religious and interest groups occasioned by marginalization, tragic fallacy, religious intolerance, suspicion, and a cognitive disconnection from the concept of “One Nigeria”. The concept – *One Nigeria* – has become improbable, unsustainable, unbelievable and impracticable among many Nigerians; consequently, many Nigerians have become less patriotic or completely unpatriotic towards Nigeria, instead they profess collective identity on the basis of

ethnic, religious, social or political affiliation. A confirmation of this can be logically deduced from the incessant demonstrations by the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger-Delta (MEND) led by Henry Okah, the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) led by Nnamdi Kanu and a faction of the Yoruba people led by Chief Sunday Adeyemo, popularly known as Sunday Igboho.

Several factors, divided into external and internal, have been identified as threats to unity in Nigeria. Notable among them are injustice, corruption, inequitable distribution of resources, religious fanaticism, intolerance, bigotry and political instability. It is no news that a nation devoid of unity cannot progress, develop and advance economically, socially and politically in this post modern world. Bearing this in mind, the Federal

Government of Nigeria has formulated policies, established agencies, and instituted schemes in a bid to quell the devastating consequences of disunity; few of governmental interventions to stem the tide of disunity and promote unity as well as brotherliness among Nigerians are: Federal Character Principle, Unity Schools, National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) Scheme, and Ministry of Information and National Orientation. However, the paradoxical reality is that governmental efforts have not achieved the desired results.

Some stakeholders in the education sector: policy makers, teachers, lecturers, parents and students have opined that what is really lacking in the system, governmental efforts to tackle and contain disunity, is the effective utilization of Christian Religious Education with its inherent potency to promote national unity and cohesion. Christian Religious Education has not been fully harnessed by the government, at all levels, because little attention is given to Christian Religious Studies, and it is also regarded as a less important subject in the school curriculum. It is therefore pertinent to have a cursory look at the concept of Christian Religious Education as well as discuss and point out ways by which it can be effectively utilized in a developing and heterogeneous nation like Nigeria.

Disunity in Nigeria: A Historical Overview

The history of political distrust in Nigeria as a country has been traced to the works of the imperialists and cultural predators who preyed on Nigerians' hospitable nature. In 1884, the British occupied what would later become the Northern and Southern Protectorates; and by 1903, the British controlled the vast territories, occupied by different tribes which make up modern Nigeria, as two separate administrative blocs: the Northern and Southern

Protectorates. Later on, the administrative need engendered by the burden of administration made the colonizers under the leadership of Sir, Lord Fredrick Lugard collapse the two protectorates, with their peculiarities – religion, culture and traditional system of governance, into one country; this, consequently, allowed the rich south to effectively subsidize for the less economically viable North.

January 1, 1914 is a significant date in the history of Nigeria; on this day, Sir, Lord Fredrick Lugard who was the Governor of both Protectorates (Southern and Northern) signed a document consolidating the two, thereby creating modern Nigeria. Many scholars of Nigerian history noted that Lugard only promoted the supremacy of the North over the South. Falola captures this very brilliantly by referring to the consolidation as a 'melodrama of arranged marriage' among culturally, linguistically and ethno-religiously diverse peoples which fanned the flame mutual distrust and ethnocentrism. The acorn seed of suspicion was planted at the time through the agency of Colonial administrators; now, it has fully grown into an oak tree of distrust and disunity. So, the problem of disunity and unifying national identity began from this time. This is further solidified in the words of Billy J Dudley as cited by Falola that to understand the politics of Nigeria, one must understand the politics of Northern Nigeria. From Independence in 1960, the problem of ethnocentrism occasioned by a feeling of marginalization raised its ugly head. Political and economic challenges also did a lot of damage to the unity of Nigeria.

On January 15th 1966, Major Kaduna Nzeogwu, Emmanuel Ifeajuna and other junior army officers led a coup d'état which was given both tribal and religious colorations; the North saw it as a direct attack on them by the Christians and southerners; this disposition was justified

on the grounds that most of the political leaders whose lives were claimed by the coup were of the Northern descent and Muslims. This further accentuated the already politically and religiously tensed country. The coup was followed by the Civil War of 1967 in quick succession. From 6th July, 1967 to 15th January, 1970, the civil war was fought; this was led by Odumegwu Ojukwu. Millions of lives and property were lost to the war. There is no gainsaying that this war did a great damage to the unity of Nigeria. When it eventually came to an end, General Gowon said there was “no victor, no vanquished”.

From this time on, all government regimes since the end of the war have made national unity their priority. They have put in place programmes and policies aimed at promoting unity. Yet, the gaps between the various ethnic, political and religious groups become wider daily. Intolerance, quest for self determination, and many others have led to self agitations. Since the return to democracy in 1999, violent protests have rocked the country thereby undermining and threatening the unity, peace, progress and stability of Nigeria.

Meaning and Nature of Christian Religious Education

Religion is defined from numerous perspectives. In all, it spreads over the concept of systems of faith, belief, worship and practice which make dynamic impact on human life. It also comprises beliefs and practices through which human beings gain experience of that which lies beyond the world of their ordinary experience. Typically, it focuses on an Ultimate or Absolute, thought of as God (Abe 2008). Religion also has to do with the outward arts or forms by which human beings indicate their recognition of the existence of a god or of gods having power over their destiny, to whom obedience, service and honour are due. In addition, it is the feeling

or expression of human love, fear or awe of some super human and over-ruling powers whether by profession of being, observance of rites and ceremonies or the conduct of life.

Religious Education is understood in different ways. First, it means the type of education that a religious body such as a Church or Mosque provides for adherents. In this context, it means being indoctrinated into a particular worldview. Second, it means a discipline that is theological in scope and content, and is offered in a school setting. In general term, Religious Education has to do with teaching about the beliefs, doctrines and practices of a particular religious tradition.

History of Christian Religious Education in Nigeria

The history of Christian Religious Education in Nigeria is also synonymous with the history of Christianity in Nigeria. The first attempt to introduce Christianity in Nigeria was in the sixteenth century by Roman Catholic Jesuit priests from Portugal. However, they could not make much impact. Church Historians agree that Christianity began in Nigeria precisely in 1842 (Jaiyeola 2017). The missionary that first landed in Nigeria through Badagery was the Wesleyan Missionary that came on the 24th September, 1842 followed by Church Missionary Society and other denominations followed. They stopped the killing of twins with the help of notable Africans such as King Eyo II of Efik land in Calabar, promoted legal trade, established hospitals, maternity centres, vocational centres, dispensaries and schools. The teaching of Christian Religious Education can be dated to the first half of the nineteenth century.

Various Christian denominations taught the Bible and Catechism along with arithmetic, sciences and the languages (both native and

foreign) in their respective schools. These schools enjoyed an unprecedented support from the missions since they were the brain children of the missionaries. Primarily, schools were established at inception for religious purposes: to advance the ideology of the mission, to convert the 'heathens', to indoctrinate, and to enlighten and salvage the natives living in the so called 'Dark Continent'. However, the secondary rationale for establishing schools was to train apprentices who would work with the colonial government to implement governmental policies. Since then and till now, the subject has remained a part of the Nigerian educational curriculum at all levels of education, primary, secondary and tertiary. It has, nevertheless, gone through several reviews which make it more robust in scope and content.

The syllabi for Christian Religious Knowledge were drawn by the Federal and State Ministries of Education since the 1950s. These syllabi prepared students for the subject in the Senior School Certificate Examinations. With the advent of ecumenical movements such as the Northern Christian Association, Christian Council of Nigeria and most importantly the Christian Association of Nigeria in 1976, various denominations established joint committees that prepared new syllabi that were adopted by all schools. When Nigeria adopted the 6-3-3-4 system of education in 1984, all syllabi were reviewed by subject panels set up by the Nigerian Education Research Council in affiliation with the Ministry of Education. The Christian Religious Studies syllabi cover mainly doctrines, moral and ethical teachings which are needed by all to lead righteous lives. All these point to the fact that the Christian Religious Education can be used as a tool for sustainable change and promotion of unity in Nigeria.

Importance of Christian Religious Education

A popular adage says "Educate men without religion and you make them clever devils". Human tendencies are always towards evil; as such, it is the aim of religion to check these tendencies. Religious and moral standards are the hope of the world. Man is the only known religious being, and there is something in him that makes him look up to God. To neglect this side of his nature is to restrict the most important side of his development.

Core values such as equality, respect for human dignity and hard work can be imparted to students through Christian Religious Education. It develops the students mentally, intellectually, physically, psychologically, culturally and spiritually. It also makes students to be tolerant of religions other than theirs. Lawal (2010) opined that every subject has its unique values and importance. This scholar noted further that the uniqueness of Christian Religious Education emerges from its dual function. It is a subject which develops the students' intellectual ability and moral character. This subject helps to inject sanity into the society and cultivate citizens who acknowledge metaphysical sanctions.

Problems Confronting Christian Religious Education in Nigeria

Onovughe and Mordi (2017) identified some of the major problems confronting Christian Religious Education as inadequate qualified teachers for the subject, lackadaisical attitude of students, inadequate Instructional materials, lack of enthusiasm on the part of the teachers and inferiority complex among teachers of subject, Christian Religious Education in Nigeria. Others are non-conducive learning atmosphere, unfavourable government policies, and shortages of man power in teacher training institutions.

Some Biblical Instances of Unity

“You are better off to have a friend than to be all alone, because then you will get more enjoyment out of what you earn. If you fall, your friend can help you. But if you fall without having a friend nearby, you are really in trouble” Ecclesiastes 4:9-10. CEV.

Love is one of the principal characters of God, the Old and New Testaments are replete with instructions that emphasize the indispensability of love in the larger society; love manifests in different dimensions which include, marriage, friendship, and partnership. In Ecclesiastes 4:9-10 as stated above, friendship is encouraged because of its usefulness in the time of great devastation. Friendship is not limited by ethnic affiliation nor religious conviction; this is indeed a value that should be promoted among Nigerians. To adherents of Christianity, the Holy Bible, the immutable and eternal truth (word of God), is the reference and content book which Christians should obey. Christian Religious Education revolves largely around the Holy Bible. It provides divine laws and guides for the totality of man’s existence. It is unique, authentic, and its principles and ethical teachings are unparalleled and unrivalled. This has made the Church attach divine and canonical authority to it. It also gives us an inspired picture of God and His character.

In the Old Testament, Unity is highly emphasized and upheld as a veritable value of the human society. In fact, the Hebrew word for unity is transliterated as ECHAD and it appears close to one thousand times there. It refers to oneness in reference to the nature and character of God. In the New Testament, HENOTES means unity in the sense of unanimous agreement. This shows clearly that unity is a law and commandment of God. It is therefore

necessary to itemize some instances Biblical portraying unity.

Tower of Babel Episode, Genesis 11:1-9

Biblically, everyone in the world spoke the same language. The people agreed to build a city with a tower that reaches to the sky. The project commenced but God confused them by making them speak different languages. Eventually, the project stopped. This episode shows clearly that no feat is difficult to attain if there is unity.

The walk of Joshua and Israel around Jericho, Joshua 6

Moses led Israel out of the Egyptian bondage and Joshua the son of Nun succeeded him after his death. While Israel was camped at Gilgal, Joshua came near Jericho and Yahweh promised victory over Jericho. The Israelites were commanded to march slowly round the city once a day for six days, taking along the sacred chest and having seven priests walking in front of it. On the seventh day, they were to march slowly around the town seven times while the priests blew their trumpets and everyone shouted. The people obeyed and Yahweh granted them victory over Jericho. Despite the fact Israel had twelve tribes, they were united, and they overcame their challenges.

The work of Nehemiah and Israel to rebuild the walls of Jerusalem, Nehemiah 3

As a result of Judah’s sins, she continued to disintegrate politically. Despite series of warnings from Prophets like Jeremiah, Amos, Hosea and others, the people never heeded. From 597 to 586 BC, Nebuchadnezzar lunched series of attacks on Judah. Eventually, she was taken into exile in 586 BC. The walls of Jerusalem and the city gates were burnt down by fire. During the exilic period, the Jews realized their folly and prayed to Yahweh for forgiveness. In 538BC, Cyrus granted the

Jews relative freedom like other nations who had been deported to Babylon to return to their lands. So, Nehemiah demonstrated patriotism by fasting and praying for forgiveness from Yahweh. He later inspected the ruined walls and encouraged the people to rebuild it. Eventually, the people collaborated to rebuild it despite all odds. When he called for the reconstruction of the temple, the Jews in exile agreed unanimously, without a divided spirit, to rebuild it. The unity helped them fend-off the opposers (Samballant and Tobias) who were hell-bent on thwarting the process.

The Building of the Second Temple, Ezra 3-6

Ezra 1:3-4 notes that the whole exilic community was expected to support the rebuilding of the Temple with various gifts. Sheshbazzar led the first caravan of twelve heads of the houses of Israel, the early returnees from Babylon to Jerusalem. Later on, priests, Levites, singers and other officials joined them. Despite the Samaritan conflict, the work was completed and it was dedicated.

The Ninevites' Repentance. Jonah 3:1-12

Nineveh was the capital of the great Assyrian empire. God sent Jonah to proclaim to the people that if they never repented, judgment and punishment was inevitable. After much hesitation, Prophet Jonah reluctantly proclaimed God's message to the inhabitants of the city. The people of Nineveh believed God's message, fasted, prayed and dressed in sack clothes. Even their king left his palace and sat in the dust. When Yahweh saw that they had repented, He had mercy on them and refrained from punishing them.

The Pentecost Episode, Acts 2: 1-47

After Jesus' resurrection, he appeared to his disciples for forty days after which he

ascended into heaven. He had told his disciples to wait for the descent of the Holy Spirit. As such, they tarried in Jerusalem, praying in unity in the Upper room. When the Spirit descended upon them, they began to speak in all the languages of the Mediterranean world and this drew the attention from those who witnessed the event. After Peter's sermon, three thousand people joined the Church.

Biblical Instances of Unity: Lessons for Nigeria

We have pointed out that the Bible emphasizes the need for unity in all its ramifications. Nigeria can certainly learn vital lessons from the various Biblical instances earlier itemized. It therefore becomes pertinent to discuss them in details. The Tower of Babel episode clearly shows that if all ethnic and religious groups in the country can come together like in the ancient times to face and surmount challenges bedevilling the nation.

Initially, Yahweh knew they could record success with the building project, He caused disunity among them by scattering their languages and this halted the project permanently. This is a lesson for Nigerians because if we do not eschew our ethnic, political and religious differences, the project of building a viable nation may not come to reality. As such, the task of nation-building is the collective responsibility of all and sundry.

Furthermore, Nigeria can learn a lesson from how Joshua and the Israelites came together to fight various wars of conquest on their way to the promise land. Jericho, a walled city, was eventually besieged and conquered by them after initial hiccups. The problems confronting Nigeria can be likened to the wall of Jericho which can be pulled down if proper measures are put in place.

Nigeria can also learn from how the people of Judah united to rebuild the walls of Jerusalem which had been pulled down and burnt by fire as well as the second Temple. For the people, these two monuments were considered to be very crucial to the continued existence of their nation. Thus, Nigerians must be patriotic so as to achieve her set goals. Development can never take place in an atmosphere of disunity and discord. Like Nehemiah, our leaders must carry everyone along in probity and accountability.

Just as the people of Nineveh demonstrated genuine repentance through unity, Nigerians must turn a new leaf by refraining from vices such as murder, bribery, money laundering, ritual killings, cyber fraud, false pretences, examination malpractices, tribalism, favouritism, nepotism and many others. The Pentecost episode also teaches Nigerians that God answers the prayers of people who dwell together in unity. After Peter's speech on that day, many people joined the Church. Nigeria can also become a choice destination for people seeking better living conditions if proper measures are put in place.

How Christian Religious Education can be effectively utilized for Unity in Nigeria

Christians are the Salt of the earth and Light of the world. Hence, Christian Religious Education promotes human values and principles such as righteousness, justice, discretion, prudence, love, mercy, forgiveness, honesty, patience and many others. These principles can be effectively utilized to promote unity in an ethno-religious, diverse and populous nation like Nigeria in the following ways itemized below;

- **Regular Review and Update of Christian Religious Education Syllabi**

The syllabi for Christian Religious Education should be regularly reviewed and updated by subject panels so as to lay emphasis and reflect the theme of unity. Furthermore, the syllabi should be planned to include topics on tolerance for people of other cultures, ethnic and religious traditions.

- **Seminars and Workshops**

Higher institutions, Ecumenical movements and various Christian denominations should regularly organize seminars, workshops and rallies to sensitize and educate members of the general public on the need for unity among different ethnic groups. Joint committees should be set up to meet regularly and issue communiqués on the importance of unity

- **Teacher Training**

Generally, there is a lackadaisical attitude towards Christian Religious Education on the part of the government. This has made the subject unattractive to admission seekers into our tertiary institutions. Hence, government should do more to make people develop interest in Christian Religious Studies as a subject. Furthermore, teachers should be properly motivated and remunerated. This will make the subject attractive to admission seekers into our tertiary institutions.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The call for unity is a *sin qua non* towards national development. Government at all levels should therefore leave no stone unturned in placing more emphasis on unity and peaceful co-existence. This can be realized by placing high premium on tolerance through Christian Religious Education. If this is done, Nigerians irrespective of socio-political or ethnic

backgrounds would become acquainted and acclimatized with necessary values, skills and attitudes needed to promote unity.

There is no gainsaying that disunity retards the progress of any nation. As such, Nigerians need to regularly examine themselves upon the scales of Biblical principles. They need to be constantly educated that the mind of God is unity in all ramifications. The amalgamation which took place in 1914 is not a mistake but a divine will, plan and purpose. So, all hand must be on deck to accord Christian Religious Education its proper place in our society.

References

- Abe, G.O. (2008). *Religion and Cultural Heritage in Contemporary Society: In Perspectives in Religious Studies*. Amazon Prints and Publications.
- Byanruhaga, C. (2018, November 23). Essential Approaches to Christian Religious Education. *Globethics*. <http://www.globethics.net/publications>.
- Contemporary English Version of The Holy Bible (1996), Thomas Nelson, Inc.
- Falola, T. & Dauda, B. (2017). *Decolonizing Nigeria, 1945-1960: Politics, Power, and Personalities*. Pan African University Press.
- Jaiyeola, A.A.C (2017). *Christian Religion As A Tool For Sustainable Change In Nigeria: An Analysis of Church Reformation In The 16th Century*. In The Change Agenda: Implications on the Nigerian State. Ojebode, P.A Ojebode and Olatunji, S.A (Eds). Omo-Oje Press and Publishers.
- Lawal, B.O. (2010, November 23). *Factors Affecting Achievement of Students in Senior Secondary Schools Certificate Examination in*

Christian Religious Studies. In African Research Review, An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal. Vol.4, No. 17. <http://www.afrevjo.com>.

Uche, E. U. & Okonkwo, C. (2020), *Nigeria and the Challenges of National Unity*. Conference Proceedings of INTCESS 2020- 7th International Conference on Education and Social Sciences held on 20th -22nd January, 2020. <http://www.researchgate.net/publications>. Nov 23, 2023.